

Reconstruction of Lithology Profile in Absence of Formation Cuttings and Logging While Drilling in an Overpressured Sequence: A Fit for Purpose Approach

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ABSTRACT

Lithology identification during drilling is the first step in formation evaluation for oil and gas exploration. In exceptional cases, both formation cuttings and logging while drilling data may be unavailable for a section of the drilled area due to various unavoidable reasons. Essentially, the rate of penetration serves as a preliminary approximation for distinguishing between drilled lithologies; however, it is ineffective when controlled drilling occurs in an overpressured section. Variations in drilling parameters will affect mechanical logs by lowering the drilling exponent and sigmalog in coarser clastics compared to finer clastics. It is recognized that as pressures increase, lower mechanical log values will be evident in finer clastics than in the underlying coarser clastics. In a deep onshore exploration, a high pressure, high temperature (HPHT) well located in the Coastal Swamp depositional belt of the Niger Delta in West Africa had to employ slim hole drilling techniques in the deeper Agbada Formation. The Logging while drilling (LWD) tools were positioned significantly offset from the bit. A kick occurred in the overpressured section, and well control activities prevented the normal circulation of cuttings to the shale shaker, rendering cuttings unavailable for analysis.

Real-time pore pressure prediction using drilling-based techniques was inverted to interpret lithology. Mechanical log parameters were calculated and calibrated with the immediately overlying drilled section, where cuttings and LWD logs were available. The integration of Pore Pressure and Lithology Prediction was pursued by employing a variant of mechanical specific energy, the drilling rate to applied weight on bit ratio (ROP/WOB), for coherence and quality checks. The challenge of lithology identification was successfully addressed, enabling the creation of an inferred lithology profile for the unlogged section that also lacked drill cuttings, clarifying the kick zone lithology. This interpreted lithology is a crucial aspect of characterizing the formations. It offers a clear understanding of sedimentation patterns and related seismic responses for future exploration in the depositional belt. The cost-effective fit-for-purpose approach is a robust exploration practice.

Key words: Lithology, HPHT, Exploration, Kick, LWD, Dc exponent, Sigmalog, MSE, Fit for purpose, Geological model, Exploration practice.

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INTRODUCTION

The identification of lithology is crucial in petroleum exploration engineering. Identifying lithology during drilling is the primary step in formation evaluation. Recognizing reservoir lithology is essential for reservoir characterization, calculating reserves, and geological modeling. In certain exceptional cases, both formation cuttings and LWD data may be unavailable in a part of the drilled section for various unavoidable reasons. The absence of these fundamental elements challenges any interpreter to decipher the lithology profile of the drilled section. The rate of penetration can serve as a preliminary approximation to distinguish drilled lithology, although this becomes ineffective during controlled drilling in an overpressured section. Mechanical logs, such as drilling exponent and sigmalog, effectively provide pore pressure estimates while drilling. These logs account for the effects of drilling parameters such as weight on bit, rotation speed, hole diameter, and mud density. In an overpressured sequence, the differential pressure between mud and formation is nearly balanced. This impacts the drillability of rocks, and maintaining a constant drilling rate will lead to variations in other drilling parameters. For redundancy, the lithology identification method based on the mechanical specific energy principle, which accounts for variations in drilling parameters, was also analyzed.

Why is lithology important?

The first step in formation evaluation is identifying lithology while drilling. This process is crucial and depends on the expertise of geologists. Lithology identification is a fundamental task in formation evaluation, necessary for recognizing and differentiating various lithologies, which is essential for exploring and characterizing reservoirs. The connection to hydrocarbon potential lies in the fact that oil typically occurs in lithologies with suitable porosity and permeability. Insights into rock properties help estimate porosity, water saturation, and permeability. This knowledge forms the foundation for stratigraphy, which is vital for dividing rock sequences and enabling mapping and correlations. As a decision-making tool, it supports core selection, off-bottom test decisions, and well abandonment or casing. Thus, knowledge of lithology is essential in geological evaluations. Conventional lithology recognition mainly relies on human experience. Traditionally, identifying lithology has primarily depended on visual observation, relying on personnel expertise to correlate engineering data. Recognition accuracy hinges on the technical staff's skill, which can lead to delays in response time^I. Determining lithology using downhole tools mainly involves employing logging instruments to collect data on downhole formations and evaluate information related to these formations. The lithological data obtained through this method is considered more reliable. It serves as the basis for calculating reservoir parameters (including porosity, shale volume, and permeability), as well as for conducting geological research such as formation correlation, sedimentary modeling, and predicting favorable zones, among others^{II}.

Rock Typing at Well Sites

Drill cutting samples provide the most continuous source of physical rock data before and after drilling. This process involves a semi-quantitative visual method to describe rock and pore characteristics through cuttings, cores, and microscopic examination. The observed

attributes include visual porosity, clay and cement types, grain size, distribution, sorting, consolidation, and grain relief. Rock typing extends beyond merely sorting rocks; it connects geology, geophysics, and reservoir engineering for specific purposes (Figure 1). It helps create models, estimate permeability, and develop functions tailored to particular issues. There is no single method that fits all scenarios, as geologists, geophysicists, and reservoir engineers benefit from customized approaches. The reservoir description approach integrates geology, petrophysics, and physics based on log measurements and core calibration^{III}.

Figure 1: Reservoir Description^{III}

Regional Geology

The Niger Delta Province in southern Nigeria is an extensional rift basin defined by clastic sedimentation upto 12 km thick. It covers an area of 300,000 km² and encompasses the Tertiary Niger Delta Petroleum System. Three primary depositional cycles have been recognized in the Tertiary Niger Delta deposits^{IV}. The first two cycles involved primarily marine deposition, beginning with a middle Cretaceous marine event and concluding with a Paleocene transgression. The second cycle, spanning from late Paleocene to Eocene, resulted in the formation of a “true” delta. The last cycle consists of six depoblets, shaped by structural changes and sediment patterns. Sedimentary deposits in the Niger Delta basin are categorized into three main units: the Akata Formation (Paleocene to Recent), the Agbada Formation (Eocene to Recent), and the Benin Formation (Oligocene to Recent)^V. These formations are younger, located further into the basin, illustrating the delta's growth toward the Atlantic Ocean. The geology is complex due to movements in the underlying shale layers, which led to normal faults and alterations in sediment flow^V. The upper Akata Formation is a key source rock of oil, with potential source rocks also found in both the Agbada and Akata formations.

The Tertiary section is characterized by high sand-shale ratios. The following Figure-2 depicts the depositional belts and the stratigraphy of the Niger Delta.

Figure 2: Depositional belts and Stratigraphy of Niger Delta^{IV,V}

HPHT Definition

HPHT, or High Pressure, High Temperature, refers to Wells with temperatures over 150°C and pressures above 69 MPa(10,000psi)(Figure 3). Advances have led to Ultra HPHT and Extreme HPHT classification^{VI}.

Figure 3: HPHT classification^{VI}

HPHT Exploration Drilling in Niger Delta

The deep drilling HPHT exploration project entails examining five oil and gas fields situated across approximately 650 square km in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. These fields were identified in the 1970s; however, they were not fully developed at that time due to their primary composition of gas, which had minimal demand in Nigeria during that period. Previous exploration campaigns had only penetrated the uppermost HPHT gas reservoir in a major coastal deposition belt field. The conceptual geological model of the HPHT prospect and its surroundings is illustrated in Figure 4. Exploration drilling targeted the deeper Agbada HPHT reservoirs.

Figure 4: Exploration model for Coastal swamp HPHT well, Niger Delta

Real-time Challenges at a key HPHT exploration well

The challenges arose following a kick in the slim hole. The kick in the HPHT environment hindered cuttings sampling for the last 30 ft, along with the unlogged formation of 46 ft. The LWD tool configuration resulted in 46 ft of drilled formation remaining unlogged. Wireline logs could not be obtained due to the well's hostile conditions. Lithology identification serves as the foundation for exploration and reservoir evaluation. The intelligent and precise identification of underground lithology became a crucial issue for geologists and engineers. Analyzing the lithology, including the causative factors of the kick and the bed thickness of the last 30 feet, using the available drilling data, provided a remedy. After the kick, the well reached a decision point to assess whether it was safe to continue drilling or to terminate the well. Traditional methods for lithology identification, such as cuttings logging and well logging, were rendered unfeasible due to the kick and the subsequent well control measures. Lithology plays a key role in understanding and predicting overpressures.

LWD Tool Configuration

The LWD resistivity tool was located approximately 52 ft above the bit, and there were no near-bit tools deployed. The gamma ray, which was used as a lithology indicator, was located 44 ft above the bit (Figure 5).

Figure 5: LWD configuration deployed in the well

Critical Unknowns

The LWD availability and the master log record of the drill cuttings illustrating the challenge are given in Figure 6.

Figure 6: LWD log and Master log of the HPHT well, red circles indicate the intervals with data absence

Real-Time Lithology Identification Using Drilling Data Drilling-based Pore pressure prediction

The log-based technique in vogue could not be carried out for want of shale resistivity picks. The drilling data was examined and drilling exponent, sigmalog, and ROP/WOB ratio were computed based on normalized rate of penetration (ROP) from the Bingham drilling model^{VII} with respect to the parameters weight on bit (WOB), rotary speed (RPM), and bit diameter.

$$R = aN^e (W/B)^d$$

where R = penetration rate (ft/hr), N = rotary speed (rpm), W = WOB (lbs.), B = bit diameter (in.)
 a = matrix strength constant, d = formation drillability, e = rotary speed exponent

However, the conventional techniques of the Dc-Exponent and Sigma Log were applied simultaneously on a routine basis, supplementing log-based prediction. Mechanical Specific Energy (MSE) has emerged as a viable alternative, especially in complex lithologies such as carbonates. Despite its theoretical advantages, MSE is still not widely used in practical drilling operations. Considering the task at hand, a variant of MSE in the form of ROP/WOB was attempted

as a quality check application to the conventional Dc-Exponent and Sigma Log after the well encountered the kick.

Dc-Exponent: The corrected D exponent is based on the theory of shale compaction, which proves ineffective in carbonates and heterogeneous formations due to insufficient porosity-pressure correlations. The 'd' exponent is a method used to normalize the influence of drilling parameters on ROP, aiming to provide a representative measurement of 'drillability'. It is exclusively applied in mudstone intervals. Jordan and Shirley^{VIII} introduced the concept of the 'd' exponent for pore pressure detection by normalizing factors (WOB, rotary speed, bit diameter) that affect the rate of penetration (ROP). When establishing a normal compaction trend (NCT) in shales, the 'd' exponent increases linearly with depth in normal pressure intervals. Upon entering overpressure intervals, the 'd' exponent tends to deviate from the NCT, exhibiting a decreasing trend. Jordan and Shirley^{VIII} modified Bingham's equation to the following form:

$$\text{D exponent} = [\log (R / 60N)] / [\log (12W / 1000 B)]$$

Rehm and McClendon^{IX} proposed the corrected d exponent to account for changes in mud weight to Jordan and Shirley's modified Bingham equation.

$$\text{Dc} = \text{d exponent} * (\text{normal pressure gradient/density of the drilling fluid in use})$$

Sigma Log: Belotti and Gerard^X utilized the Sigmalog concept (a parameter for rock strength) to determine pore pressure, which depends on the interconnection between rock strength, pore pressure, and formation lithology. Similarly, one can chart the changes in sigmalog with depth and establish a trend line. The Sigmalog seeks to address the shortcomings of the 'd' exponent while drilling through overpressured sequences of mixed lithologies, such as limestones, marls, and silty mudstones. The Sigmalog represents the variation of the Sigma Factor (total rock strength) with depth. The efficiency and limitations of the Sigmalog closely resemble those of the 'd' exponent, particularly in relation to lithology.

$$\text{Sigma} = ((W^{0.5} \times N^{0.25}) / (Dh \times \text{ROP}^{0.25})) \text{ where Dh, the bit diameter.}$$

The Mechanical Specific Energy (MSE) model, introduced by Teale^{XI}, measures the energy required to break and remove a unit volume of rock. It is widely used for real-time assessments of drilling efficiency, optimizing drilling parameters, identifying inefficient working conditions downhole, and determining lithology^{XII, XIII}. MSE correlates the energy consumed by a drill bit with the rock's effective stress and pore pressure, where effective stress is defined as the difference between total vertical stress and pore pressure. Normal pressure and effective stress influence changes in rock strength, while lithology variations through the geological section can significantly impact rock properties. The fundamental principle is that intervals exhibiting overpressure and reduced effective stress require less energy for drilling compared to normally pressured intervals at an equivalent depth. To enhance drilling efficiency, empirical Rate of Penetration (ROP) models should incorporate geomechanical data. The integration of MSE and ROP models was successfully achieved by Hasan et al. in 2020^{XIV}. However, this concept was not applied to pore pressure prediction while drilling.

Given the unconstrained nature of the pressures in the deep section of the Niger Delta, an integrated approach was employed, where pore pressure predictions are constrained by

geological insights. The integrated pore pressure plot of the well is shown in Figure 7, indicating the kick at the well bottom. This kick served as the calibration for the deep pressure ramp. It is reasonable to anticipate that changes in overpressure are likely to coincide with these widespread sealing horizons. A pore pressure ramp adjusts the pore pressure profile from one condition to a higher pore pressure scenario across a depth interval, which in our case lies within the unlogged, sample-devoid interval (Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 7: Pore pressure plot of the HPHT well

Reverse Modelling for Lithology Prediction from Pore Pressure Prediction

The pore pressure prediction indicated that the kick was a consequence of a pressure ramp at the well bottom. This suggests that there is an impermeable seal as well as reservoir rock in the unlogged, sample-devoid section. The lithology changes throughout the section can significantly affect rock properties. The major takeaway from the kick and pore pressure prediction is that important permeable and impermeable layers are present and crucial to exploration.

The drilling-based pore prediction from Dc-Exponent and Sigmalog is effective for mudstone and various lithologies, respectively. To ensure redundancy, a variant of MSE, the ROP/WOB ratio, was computed to quality-check the Dc exponent and Sigmalog results. Variations in drilling parameters affected the mechanical logs, leading to a decrease in the drilling exponent and Sigmalog in coarser clastics compared to finer clastics. It is well recognized that approaching high pressures results in lower mechanical log values in finer clastics than in the overlying coarser

Lithology Distinction from Drilling Exponent

Drillability of shales: The drilling rate at standard operating conditions decreases with depth but increases when pore pressure increases due to reduced compaction. A lower Dc exponent expected in coarser clastics was used to distinguish sands and shales (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Drilling exponent (Dc exponent) of the HPHT section that lacked logs and samples

Lithology Distinction from Sigma Log

The rock strength of shales in an overpressure environment is expected to be higher than coarser clastics, allowing their distinction (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Sigmalog of the HPHT section that lacked logs and samples

Lithology Distinction from a Simplistic Variant of MSE

Given that the mechanical characteristics and crushing mechanisms of rocks with different lithologies vary significantly, an enhanced ROP can be achieved when the drilling parameters (such as WOB, rotations per minute (RPM), bit type, etc.) align with the specific rock lithology being drilled. Given the controlled drilling, the ROP/WOB ratio is expected to be higher in coarser clastics, and it was obtained, enabling the distinction of sand and shale based on the energy or work required to pulverize a volume of rock by drilling (Figure 10).

Figure 10: ROP/WOB ratio of the HPHT section that lacked logs and samples

Integration of D_c , Σ , and ROP/WOB for Coherence

Relying solely on real-time drilling parameters for lithology forecasting often leads to uncertainty due to multicollinearity and ambiguous data interpretations. To address these challenges, we combine real-time drilling information used for pore pressure prediction through three different methods, which helps reduce uncertainty. The valuable insights gained from the lithological sequences of sections drilled in the immediately overlying continuous deposition section reveal sedimentary patterns that enhance predictions. The known lithology provided the calibration, and we examined the trend. The method showed overall convergence, except for a depth uncertainty

range of 5 to 6 ft at both the upper and lower sections of the second sand. Nonetheless, the stacked sedimentary pattern could be interpreted (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Integrated plot of Dc, Sigma, and ROP/WOB ratio of the section that lacked logs and samples

Reconstructed Lithology Profile

The inferred lithology profile was generated with an uncertainty band to clarify the kick zone lithology. The analysis reveals the lithology profile of the F4 section, which has a standard data gap and bottoms in reservoir lithology, resulting in the kick with the predominant circulating pressure. The re-engineering provided insight into the thickness of the porous and permeable sandstone reservoir. Additionally, the mudrock thickness could be predicted with reasonable certainty. This suggests that F4 comprises interbedded sands and shales, indicating that the well may have drilled through four sand beds. This information enhanced the accuracy of the geological model. The lithological column inferred in the F4 sand package is presented alongside a potential gamma ray response for the unlogged section, based on the response of the stacked sands resting above it (Figure 12). Therefore, the sand package constitutes a complex of interbedded sands and

shales. This contrasts sharply with the pre-drill model of a thick F4 sand unit (Figure 13). As a pressure ramp was encountered, the presence of an impermeable pressure seal is anticipated.

Figure 12: Possible Gamma ray response along with inferred lithocolumn

Figure 13: Geological Model (Schematic vs. Actual)

The boon of the fit for purpose approach

The forecast prompted a quick reassessment of the seismic outlook concerning the likelihood of thin pressured sandstone beds occurring. Kick tolerance was insufficient to continue drilling, thus halting the operation. Managing the equivalent circulating density (ECD) in the slim hole under these circumstances would be challenging, as the drilling margin narrowed significantly. A crucial requirement for the widespread implementation of real-time lithology identification is the exclusive use of real-time drilling parameters, as the traditional reliance on drill cuttings and LWD data proved ineffective in these circumstances. Essentially, a geologist at the well considers drilling parameters in their percentage logging of drill cuttings and their documentation of the master log. Our approach depended solely on drilling data for lithology identification, necessitated by the conditions encountered in the HPHT well. This enabled a prompt and cost-efficient application of the available real-time drilling data in a demanding context. Well control took four days, and the fit-for-purpose approach could be accomplished within the first six hours of the well control activity. The exploration leads for the alterations of thin bed occurrence allow for selecting the right alternative for further mapping.

Robust Exploration Practice

Figure 14: Seven best exploration practices^{XV}

The exploration of oil and gas is inherently risky. While the risk cannot be completely eliminated, it can be managed and mitigated through appropriate workflows, along with conceptual and technological advancements. Discovering new economically viable oil and gas reserves has become increasingly challenging. Based on experience, there are seven essential practices for successful oil and gas exploration (Figure 14). Three of these practices are primarily technical, two emphasize behavioral aspects, and the remaining two highlight the necessity for a cohesive, commercially-oriented business approach^{XV}.

Judicious explorers recognize the influencing factors and understand how to maximize data without exceeding its limits. The constraints imposed by insufficient data must be established.

Often, not all available data is utilized in developing subsurface realizations. Raw data transforms into information once it has been processed and interpreted. We could implement the best exploration practices in real time- technically, commercially, and behaviorally- making the no-cost innovation suitable and successful.

The fit-for-purpose approach utilized real-time adaptation, technically employing the available data to construct a plausible lithology profile, which enabled informed decision-making within the well control timeframe. As a bridge in the absence of key primary data pertaining to subsurface geology, the methodology serves as an effective means to understand lithology.

CONCLUSION

The inversion of pore pressure detection techniques that rely on drilling parameters represents a significant shift in lithology detection, particularly when other subsurface tools, such as cutting samples, are inaccessible in an HPHT environment. This method provides exceptional flexibility for lithology identification and allows for real-time adaptability. By correlating pore pressure predictions in an HPHT setting with the lithological constraints associated with different rock types, one can accurately determine the vertical distribution of rocks with a high level of reliability. This initiative demonstrates that pore pressure prediction (PPP) will continue to serve as a supplementary tool, both theoretically and practically effective in constraining lithology when cuttings and well logs are unavailable. The HPHT exploration well was supported and the analysis provided fresh leads for future exploration in the Coastal Swamp depositional belt of Niger Delta.

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